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FUNCTIONS AND AREAS OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

ФУНКЦІЇ ТА СФЕРИ ПУБЛІЧНОГО УПРАВЛІННЯ

Irina R. Kravtsova
 Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
 ORCID: 0000-0002-5405-3226
 Email: irina010699@gmail.com

Oleksandr S. Balan, Doctor of Economics, Professor
 Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
 ORCID: 0000-0001-6711-5687
 Email: shurabalan@ukr.net

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Problem statement and its importance. With the changes in Ukraine's public standards in the relations of people and the country based on the current functioning of the Constitution, the concept of managerial authority faced difficulties encountered in the formation of views, terminology, which would specifically and accurately explain the meaning of such social standards. In this context, the concept of public administration functions requires fresh development. It should be noted that in the academic sources and regulations the presentation of "functions" is used in different meanings. For example, "functions of law", "functions of state organizations", "functions of the legal process", etc. Thus, this concept is each time endowed with various peculiarities in the subordination to the branches of its use. Possesses personal qualities and meaning and presentation of "functions of public administration". Study research and publications. Scientists who emerged with management in Ukraine have recommended their own vision of the functions of public administration.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

They were devoted to their own activities Yu. P. Btiak, R. A. Luzhnyj, Yu. M. Michurinsk, Yu. M. Starilov and others. The purpose of this article is to formulate functions of public administration, proposals in the field of their systematization, an explanation of the statement formulated by scientists that one of the functions of public administration is administrative services. Description of the main used material. Function is a term that has a set of values. Translated from Latin function-execution, implementation, as well as activity, commitment, purpose, significance. In contrast to the only definitions of the rights and principles of power, in the relations of which the most differently arranged beliefs of modern scholars, the notion of functions which require their own consideration, and, moreover, the latest theoretical and methodological approaches

Балан О.С., Кравцова І.Р. Функції та сфери публічного управління. Оглядова стаття.

У статті робиться акцент на те, що за допомогою комплексності функцій знаходить власне відображення процес публічного управління. Перебуваючи взаємовпливаючими і взаємозалежними функції публічного управління складають одне ціле. Їх дослідження надає потенціал розумінню відповідних характеристик суб'єктів взаємовідносин публічного управління. Крім того підкреслюється те, що вони виконуються через форми і способи публічного управління, які визначають шляхи та засоби процесу публічного управління. У статті пропонується їх класифікація. Акцентується увага на тому, що однією з головних функцій громадського управління є адміністративна послуга.

Ключові слова: функція, сфери, публічне управління, суб'єкти, адміністративна послуга.

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The article focuses on the fact that with the help of complexity of functions the actual process of public administration is reflected. Being mutually influential and interdependent functions of public administration are one integral. Their research provides the potential for understanding the relevant characteristics of the subjects of the relationship of public administration. In addition, it is emphasized that they are executed through the forms and methods of public administration, which defines the ways and means of the process of public administration. The article proposes their classification. The focus is on the fact that one of the main functions of public administration is an administrative service.

Keywords: function, sphere, public administration, subjects, administrative service.

to their own definition, have developed in the least different way [1].

The only and widest definition of the "function" is given by V. M. Protasov. He believes that function is a function, as the influence that one must implement is one or another concept (government, law, state apparatus, science, theory, etc.) in order to find solutions to the problems that are set before it, to achieve own goals [2]. In public administration functions reflect its essence. The essence of public administration is a set of his actions, relationships, relationships. Their number and diversity say to what extent it is difficult to consider public administration.

Functions show an independent, impartial and multifunctional look and application in various areas of public administration. They are considered interdependent and interrelated and directly included in the process of public administration and form a single whole with it. All of their complex shows the management process. In this way, the functions of public administration are independent and high-quality similar elements of the work of subjects of public administration, connected with each other by the general purpose, distinctive features of realization. Functions of public administration are carried out using the form and method of public administration, which demonstrate the ways and resources of the course of public administration. Forms of public administration - this is an external representation of the actual functioning of public administration organizations. Methods of public administration - these are methods of influence of subjects of management in the subjects of management. The content, forms and methods of public administration are subject to the stabilizing influence of generally accepted measures of administrative law and thus they are administrative-legal. Each role, its essence, is determined by the purpose that appears before each public administration and the country as a whole.

The purpose is to understand the trends and the results obtained in the process of public administration. According to their content, they are impartial and are conditioned by the substantive and organizational and legal criteria of administrative processes. On the basis of the goal, the classification of functions of public administration is formed. Probable their classification depending on the subject of management, the final result, and the like. In addition, they are divided into internal (internal management of the management concept) and external (the influence of state organizations in the objects of management), economic, social, socio-educational, etc. However, classical and more popular in managerial law are their division into: a) united; b) specialized; c) auxiliary (servicing) General functions of public administration are inherent in the whole management process for the purpose of absolutely all levels of management structures.

They reflect the bigger problems of the public administration process. These include: forecasting, planning, regulation, coordination, accounting and control. Forecasting is considered to be a scientific prediction, a complete consideration of the concept,

the texture of the collaborators of the management process, its dynamics and the possibilities of formation. Forecasting is a way of making administrative decisions in order to determine the content of social processes, the status of participants in the management of the paths and the timing of achieving management goals. The forecast contains the form of an important document, which fixes the likely trends in achieving the goals of public administration.

The preparation of the plan is to find the currents and issues of development of public administration in the appropriate interval, its methods and means of their implementation, the terms of fulfillment of specific goals, material resources necessary for their superiority, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the formation of processes in the concept of public administration. The plan can be short-term, medium-term and long-term. According to the volume of issues that are solved in the course of public administration, it can be tactical and strategic. Settlement is the provision of interconnections among the structural components of managerial concepts. In public administration, it is carried out through the formation of laws, norms, standard of this or another type of management system, which are considered to be inalienable for absolutely all the accomplices of this system. Regulation is considered a system for monitoring compliance with these laws, bringing to justice the violators of laws, adjusting their behavior. The purpose of regulation is the formation of the necessary economic, legal and organizational conditions for the work of administrative systems.

Coordination will coordinate the activities of various components of management concepts of public administration. With the help of coordination, interactions are achieved between the proper skeletal units, the links of management systems, and the integrity and organization of all management activities is ensured [1]. Accounting - is the receipt, processing, research and storage of data on the location and dynamics of the formation of the administrative concept, the position of the real abilities of the accomplices of public administration, the administrative decisions and the results of their implementation. The calculation is carried out by the method of registration, comparison, comparison of certain facts about the activities of the concept of management, the presence and cost of resources, etc.

With its support, the subjects of public administration have data on the set of management objectives, the implementation of administrative decisions. Control is the formation of how the established administrative regulations are guaranteed, which together with other management functions give an opportunity to understand the results of the work performed, to prevent and eliminate deficiencies within the appointed time.

The purpose of control is to: detect errors in the management process, their timely correction and avoidance of repetition; ensuring consistency between the plans and actual actions. The special functions of public administration make it possible to determine

the features and conditions of public administration. They establish the specifics of a particular subject or object of public administration. Special (specialized) functions of public administration by types of managed objects reflect the features and conditions of management and, in the first place, the economy, socio-cultural, and administrative-political spheres. The special functions of public administration carried out by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, listed in Art. 116 of the Constitution of Ukraine.

Local state administrations in the relevant territory ensure the implementation of the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, acts of the President, the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, and other bodies of executive power; maintenance of law and order; observance of rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens. Special (specialized) functions of public administration are distinguished at all levels of sectoral management systems, for example, education and science, agriculture, armed forces, and others. Theory and History of State and Law 26 Legal Aid 3 (32) 2014 The auxiliary functions of public administration are: personnel, logistical, financial activities, clerical work, and others. The effectiveness of management activity depends on them. They provide the implementation of the first two functions of public administration, and in practice they interact with each other and form a single system of influence of the subject on the object of public administration. A separate function of public administration is an administrative service. The etymological meaning of the term "service" is defined as the special consumer cost of the labor process, expressed in a beneficial effect that meets the needs of man, team, and society.

In the right, the term "service" has begun to be used and used in the countries of the Anglo-Saxon (general) system (family) law: in England, Canada, the United States, Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands, other countries. In the countries of the Romano-Germanic system (the family) the rights to which Germany, France, the Russian Federation and other countries belong, the legal relations between the state power and the citizens are exercised through the use of such categories as "rights", "duties", "Responsibility", "authority", "function", "task" of the public administration. In Ukraine, the notion of "service" is given in various regulations, for example, in the laws: "On Citizenship", "On Citizens' Associations", "On the Bodies for the Registration of Civil Status Acts", "On Immigration", "On Patenting Certain Types of Entrepreneurial activities", "On Standardization", "On Licensing Certain Types of Economic Activities", "On Procurement of Goods, Works and Services for Public Funds", "On the Protection of Rights to Trademarks for Goods and Services", and others.

At the same time, in the listed normative legal acts of Ukraine it is used in the words "administrative, state, public, management service". His choice is related and depends on the content of the activities of public administration bodies. The main attention is drawn to the duties of public administration bodies towards citizens, through the legal provision of the

necessary conditions for the exercise of their rights, freedoms and legitimate interests. The service, as a legal term, has the following characteristics: a) it is an activity aimed at satisfying the needs of a natural or legal person; b) it is a material benefit, since it creates a beneficial effect of a material nature, has a special consumer value - a beneficial effect (satisfaction of the needs of the person); c) the service has no property expression, and therefore cannot be transferred to another person. In accordance with the Law of Ukraine "On Administrative Services" of September 6, 2012 (Clause 1, Article 1), an administrative service is the result of the exercise of authority by the entity of providing administrative services on the application of a natural or legal person, aimed at acquiring, changing or termination of the rights and / or duties of such person in accordance with the law.

For administrative law, administrative services are a new type of legal relationship between public administration bodies and individuals and legal entities. The legal construction of the term "administrative service" consists of a universal legal category "service" and "administrative" category. The content of the category "service" affects the perception of the administrative service from the standpoint of consolidating the mutual rights and obligations of both the subjects of their provision, and consumers of services. Category "administrative" refers to the sphere of social relations within which the service is provided (managerial, organizational). Such essence of administrative service determines the circle of subjects of their provision - executive bodies, local self-government bodies, and their officials [3]. Administrative services, depending on the entities that provide them, are divided into: a) government, provided by state authorities, enterprises, institutions, organizations. Public services include those provided by non-state entities in the process of implementing their delegated authority; b) municipal, provided by local authorities, communal enterprises, institutions and organizations.

Administrative services provided by the subjects of public administration in their content are managerial as they are stipulated by the authorizing authorities of the public service. IP Golosnichenko asserts that it is the organizational (managerial) character of the actions, with the help of which conditions are created for the realization of rights by private individuals and legal entities, underlies the content of administrative services [4, p. 126]. Non-administrative services are not related to the adoption of government decisions, such as medical, educational, and others. It is inappropriate to attribute to administrative services:

- the actions of public administration entities, which are carried out on their own initiative, without the involvement of the applicant;
- actions of the public administration body, which are carried out at the request of the authority;
- actions having a labor or service character;

- the actions that are related to the resolution of disputes between entities that have addressed the public administration body.

In addition, according to Art. 2 of the above Law, its operation does not apply to relations concerning:

- the implementation of state supervision (control); metrological control and supervision;
- accreditation of conformity assessment bodies;
- inquiry, pre-trial investigation;
- operational search activities;
- judicial proceedings, enforcement proceedings;
- notarial acts;
- execution of sentences;
- access to public information;
- application of legislation on the protection of economic competition;
- carrying out activities related to state secrets;
- acquisition of the right on a competitive basis;
- acquiring rights in relation to objects that are restricted in civil proceeding.

The conditions for the provision of administrative services may include: a) the right to free public discretion of the subject of public administration in carrying out appropriate actions and taking decisions; b) the right of the relevant subject to refuse to exercise his right to apply for the provision of services. Signs of administrative services are: a) they are provided only on the application of a physical or legal person. Application is a kind of appeal of a person, which contains a request (demand) for certain actions and decision making to those addressed to the appeal; b) the statement leads to a certain result, aimed at acquiring, changing or terminating the rights and duties of a person; c) an administrative service is the result of exercising power by the subject of the provision of administrative services; d) the administrative service is provided in accordance with the law.

The entities applying for administrative services are an individual, a legal entity that applies for administrative services. The subject of administrative service provision is an executive body, another state body, the authority of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, a local self-government body, and their officials authorized to provide administrative services in accordance with the law [2]. The institutional, rather than functional, criterion used in the law for the establishment of entities providing administrative services clearly indicates that other entities do not have this right. The requirements of this Law apply to providing the entity with the provision of administrative services for excerpts and extracts from registers, certificates, certificates, copies, duplicates of documents and other acts stipulated by the law, as a result of which the subject of treatment, as well as the object in his ownership, possession or use, is provided or confirmed by a certain legal status and / or fact.

Subjects of appeal have the right to receive free of charge information on administrative services and the procedure for their provision, provided by providing them with free access to the Register of

Administrative Services located on the Government Portal, the operation of the round-the-clock Governmental telephone directory, and the informing of such entities through the mass media [3]. Subjects of providing administrative services are obliged to ensure:

- the arrangement of reception areas for reception of information stands with samples of relevant documents and information to the extent sufficient to obtain administrative services without third-party assistance;
- the creation and operation of websites that contain information on the procedure for the provision of appropriate administrative services, access to the premises in which the reception of reception subjects, the availability of public transport, access roads and parking spaces;
- the implementation by public officials of the reception of the subjects of appeals in accordance with the schedule approved by the head of the relevant subject of the provision of administrative services. The number of hours of reception of subjects of appeals should be not less than 40 hours per week, including on Saturday - not less than six hours;
- providing the subject of appeal, who applied with the help of telecommunication facilities (telephone, e-mail, other means of communication), information on the procedure for the provision of administrative services;
- the publication of reference and information materials on administrative services and the free distribution of such materials in the premises where reception of the subjects of appeals is carried out;
- arrangement of a box for the submission of comments and suggestions on the quality of the provision of administrative services by the subjects, an annual analysis of such comments and proposals, taking appropriate measures.

An administrative service is considered to be provided from the moment the person receives the request personally or by post (by registered letter with the notice of service) by letter with the notice about the possibility of receiving such service to the address of the subject of appeal. In cases provided for by law, the relevant document may be sent by post (by registered letter with a statement of award) or by means of telecommunication connection. At the same time, the period of delivery of mail correspondence is not credited to the time period for the provision of administrative services. An entity providing administrative services may issue organizational and administrative acts setting its own requirements for the quality of administrative services (determining the number of hours of admission, the maximum waiting time in the queue, and other parameters for assessing the quality of providing administrative services).

Administrative services are provided by the entities providing administrative services directly, through the centers for the provision of administrative

services and / or through the Unified State Administration Services Portal. An individual, including an individual entrepreneur, is entitled to receive administrative services regardless of the registration of his place of residence or place of residence, except in cases established by law [4]. A legal entity has the right to receive administrative services at the location of such person or, in cases stipulated by law, at the place of the activity or location of the relevant facility. An application for administrative service is submitted in writing or verbally. A written application may be filed to the entity providing the administrative service personally, sent by post or in cases provided for by law, with the help of telecommunication facilities.

An entity providing administrative services may not require from the subject of circulation documents or information that is in the possession of the subject of the provision of administrative services or in the possession of state bodies, authorities of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, local self-government, enterprises, institutions or organizations, belonging to the sphere of their management. In order to receive administrative services, the entity submits documents in cases stipulated by law (if the information contained in them is not included in the relevant information databases in an amount sufficient to provide administrative services). The subject of administration of administrative services receives relevant documents or information without the participation of the subject of appeal, including through direct access to information systems or databases of other entities providing administrative services, enterprises, institutions or organizations belonging to their management.

The subject of the provision of administrative services, enterprises, institutions or organizations belonging to its management, having the documents or information necessary for the provision of administrative services, are required: 1) to provide free provision of such documents or information no later than three working days from the day of receipt of the request from the subject of the provision of the administrative service, unless otherwise provided by law; 2) take measures to develop the system of interagency electronic interaction, provide free and open access to their information systems and

databases, unless otherwise provided by law; 3) ensure, in accordance with the law, the storage and protection of information obtained as a result of the provision of administrative services.

The subject of the provision of administrative services provides the opportunity for the recipients to receive, free of charge, a sufficient number of application forms and other documents necessary to apply for the provision of administrative services, including receiving forms from the websites of the entities providing administrative services, in the centers of provision administrative services. The subject of providing administrative services provides free access to their premises, in which the reception of the subjects of appeals, including the appropriate conditions for access of persons with disabilities. An administrative service is considered to be provided from the moment the person receives the request personally or by post (by registered letter with the notice of service) by letter with the notice about the possibility of receiving such service to the address of the subject of appeal. When providing administrative services in cases stipulated by law, a fee (administrative fee) is charged.

Conclusions.

Provision of administrative services in the area of social security of citizens is carried out on a royalty-free basis. The fee for the provision of administrative services (administrative fee) is submitted by the subject of the appeal once for the whole complex of actions and decisions of the subject of the provision of the administrative services necessary for obtaining the administrative service (including the cost of the forms, the examinations carried out by the subject of the provision of the administrative service, the receipt of the lifts from registers, etc.). For the provision of administrative services, the Center for the provision of administrative services is formed - a permanent working body or structural unit of the executive body of the city, settlement council administrative services through the administrator through its interaction with the entities providing administrative services.

Abstract

The article focuses on in what case, the means of combining the functions of public administration dominates its own reflection of the actions of public administration. Being interdependent and interdependent, the functions of public administration are reunited into something single. And as a result of the research, they provide the likelihood of awareness of the distinctive features of relations between the subjects of public administration. It is told that besides how they are carried out through the form and methods of public administration. The article assumes their classification. There is a bias that the management service is considered to be the single purpose of public administration.

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